

"GPR" Project

"Development of hazard management strategies following the event of 29 October 2018 on the Rotiano stream"

Provincia Autonoma di Trento – Servizio Bacini montani

Identification of torrent control systems with potential fragility and notes on mitigation strategies

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1. Introduction

In the European Alps, the stabilization of mountain torrents through the construction of consolidation works has a long tradition. Towards the end of the nineteenth century, these structural control measures experienced substantial development, mainly as a consequence of increasing land-use pressure, which led to enhanced erosion and slope instability. This resulted, on the one hand, in higher probability of debris flows and, on the other hand, in the exposure of an increasing number of infrastructures to these damaging events (Comiti, 2012).

From the beginning of the twentieth century, protection against torrential floods and debris flows was primarily provided by the construction of permanent protection works in the upper parts of catchments, complemented by afforestation of valley slopes in order to reduce erosion and prevent the initiation of debris flows (Dell'Agnese et al., 2013; Piton et al., 2016). Due to the expansion of residential, agricultural, and industrial land use, consolidation strategies were progressively extended to a growing number of Alpine torrents and catchments. Starting from the 1960s, in Italy as well as in many other mountainous regions of Europe, consolidation works were widely constructed along torrent channels (initially in stone masonry and later in concrete, including reinforced concrete), with the aim of reducing channel gradients, preventing bed incision, and stabilizing adjacent slopes (Bruno Mazzorana et al., 2014; Galia et al., 2016).

In addition, numerous filtering check dams were installed at strategic locations within catchments, with the function of selectively retaining sediments transported within the channel, to mitigate downstream flood and debris-flow hazards. A large proportion of these structures are still in operation today.

The approach to the design and construction of consolidation works organized into *torrent control systems* is based on protection principles and objectives such as structural and economic efficiency and effectiveness, hazard reduction, and the flexibility and resilience of the system to events of different magnitudes (Mazzorana and Fuchs, 2010). However, without the implementation of appropriate maintenance strategies, the effectiveness of hazard mitigation is bound to decrease over time. Indeed, consolidation works that constitute torrent control systems exhibit a dual nature (Mazzorana and Fuchs, 2010): on the one hand, they are designed to mitigate natural hazards; on the other hand, they are themselves susceptible to damage during their service life by the very processes they are intended to mitigate (Mazzorana, 2008; Vorogushyn et al., 2009; Ballesteros Cánovas et al., 2016).

The failure of consolidation works may increase downstream hazard due to the release of large volumes of sediment and may raise the vulnerability of the entire protection system (Dell'Agnese et al., 2013). In the context of climate change, the service life of such works, combined with the residual hazard associated with their failure, may be particularly critical for the integrity of torrent control systems, especially in the case of natural events exceeding the magnitude assumed in the original design.

A reliable assessment of the condition of each individual structure and of the torrent control system as a whole is essential for understanding and predicting the evolution of flood risk within a catchment. Assessing the state and functionality of existing structures, however, requires extensive monitoring activities over a very large number of works, often located in areas that are difficult to access. This represents a significant burden in terms of costs, time, and personnel for the authorities responsible for their maintenance (Mazzorana et al., 2014). The available scientific literature proposes several methods and criteria developed by different authors to assess the condition of check dams and their associated torrent control systems (e.g. Cortes Arevalo et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2022).

Unfortunately, little is still known about the consequences of damage to protection works and about the impact associated with specific events (e.g. debris flows, debris floods, or intense bedload transport), and even less is known about how initial physical conditions may influence the response to a given event

(Dell’Agnese et al., 2013). One way to shed light on the vulnerability of protection works is through empirical field investigations, analysing a large and representative sample of consolidation works that encompass different structural conditions, event types, and intensities.

The identification of structures and torrent control systems that are susceptible to failure represents a fundamental step for the assessment of residual hazard.

Assuming the collapse of a consolidation structure, or of an entire torrent control system, implies not only the loss of functionality of the protection works, but also their contribution to the intensification of torrential processes. Moreover, the type of torrential processes involved (e.g. debris flows or torrential floods with sediment transport) is fundamental for the assessment of residual hazard associated with structural failure. Debris flows are probably the processes with the highest probability of causing sudden failure of protection works. The potential failure of consolidation works in a debris-flow torrent (especially if it occurs during a debris-flow event) may have particularly severe consequences, as also demonstrated by the events that occurred in the Rotiano catchment in October 2018.

Within the framework of the present project, activities were carried out with the following objectives:

1. to identify potentially fragile torrent control systems;
2. to define levels of priority for monitoring, maintenance, and intervention as a function of the types and age of existing consolidation works and of the different characteristics of watercourses within the territory of the Autonomous Province of Trento.

2. Methods

The identification of structures that may present critical conditions for failure within the territory of the Autonomous Province of Trento—also functional to the definition of residual hazard—requires the development of a classification methodology. In order to satisfy criteria of ease of application, repeatability, and low subjectivity, a synthetic index was developed, based on a score-based classification system that uses a subdivision into classes and numerical values assigned to those factors characterizing the structures that are considered sensitive in defining their vulnerability, and therefore useful for identifying potentially fragile torrent control systems (Fig. 1).

Fragility, as used in this report, denotes the susceptibility of torrent control works to damage or failure when subjected to torrential processes.

The final index, obtained from the summation of the scores, must be easily traceable back to the evaluation process, so as to highlight the combination of the different selected factors. Among the many factors affecting the condition of the structures, it is possible to distinguish between **internal factors** (construction-related components) and **external factors** (environmental components related to the site where the structure is located). To identify structures that may present critical conditions in terms of their protective function, the analysis was carried out in a GIS environment using ESRI ArcGIS software.

Fig. 1. Methodological framework for the classification of structures.

Internal factors were derived from the database of structures of the Autonomous Province of Trento, whereas external factors were obtained from the cartographic datasets available for the Autonomous Province of Trento (Tab. 1).

Table 1. Factors selected for the application of the index

Factor	
1	Structure age (year of construction)
2	Structure height
3	Structure construction material
Internal factors of the structure (structure database)	
4	Landslide hazard
5	Substrate (geo-lithological map 1:10000)
6	Instability index
External factors affecting the structure	

The classification of each factor was based on the identification of thresholds capable of clearly discriminating among classes. As shown in Table 2, three classes were defined for each factor, and a fragility score was assigned to each class (1 = low, 2 = moderate, 3 = high).

Table 2. Definition of classes

Internal Factors	External Factors
<p><u>Structure age (factor 1)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Year >2000 = class 1 • Year 1970-2000 = class 2 • Year <1970 = class 3 • N.A. = class 3 <p><u>Structure height (factor 2)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Height < 3m = class 1 • N.A. = class 2 • Height >3m = class 3 <p><u>Construction material (factor 3)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stone = class 1 • Concrete = class 1 • Wood = class 2 • Gabion = class 2 • Other = class 3 • N.A = class 3 	<p><u>Landslide hazard (factor 4)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N.A. = class 1 • H1 = class 1 • H2 = class 1 • H3 = class 2 • H4 = class 3 <p><u>Substrate (factor 5)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lithotype (rock) = class 1 • Other/N.A. = class 2 • Quaternary deposits = class 3 <p><u>Instability index (factor 6)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-37 = class 1 • 38-80 = class 2 • >80 = class 3

2.1 Internal factors related to the structures

The starting point for the analysis of critical conditions affecting torrent control systems is the dataset of all protection works within the Autonomous Province of Trento (check dams, chutes, embankments, etc.). For the purposes of this analysis, two types of structures were selected: **consolidation check dams** and **retention check dams**, which amount respectively to 16,793 and 337 elements in the provincial dataset.

With regard to the age of the structure, classification was carried out by identifying three time periods during which construction practices reflected the typical methodologies and technologies of the respective periods, as well as the potential degradation associated with ageing. Structures with unknown construction dates (N.A.) were conservatively assigned to the worst class.

The classification of structure height was based on a threshold value defined as 3 m, mainly in relation to the potential impact that a failure of the structure could have on downstream structures or, more generally, on the affected channel reach. For unknown values (N.A.), an intermediate class was assigned in order to balance the uncertainty associated with missing information.

The classification of construction materials aims to reflect the resistance of the structure to potential damage. Assuming that the material selected for each structure was appropriate to the characteristics of the catchment and to the mitigation objectives, and recalling that even concrete structures can suffer damage—as occurred in the case of the Rotiano stream—the definition of classes for this factor seeks to highlight those structures within a torrent control system that may be more fragile. Unknown values (N.A.) and undefined values (“Other”) were assigned to the worst class in order to avoid underestimating uncertainty due to missing information.

2.2 External factors related to the structures

External factors were identified on the basis of the following characteristics:

- landslide hazard;
- substrate type derived from the geological map;
- instability index.

The classification of landslide hazard affecting the structures is based on the *Landslide Hazard Map*, approved by Provincial Government Resolution no. 1307 of 4 September 2020, which describes and classifies the territory affected by known landslide phenomena according to the criteria and methodology approved by Resolution no. 1306 of 4 September 2020. The map defines four hazard levels (from H1 – negligible – to H4 – high), which may occur on the slopes of provincial catchments. An excerpt of this map, referring to the Cismon catchment, is shown in Figure 2.

A buffer with a radius of 10 m was conservatively applied around each structure in order to identify potential interactions with landslides, even where these are not in direct contact with the structure.

Fig. 2. Landslide hazard map of the Cision torrent catchment.

The classification of the geo-lithological substrate underlying protection works aims to highlight both the characteristics of the cross section in which a structure was built and the potential release of solid material in the event of structural failure (Fig. 3). Based on the Provincial Geo-lithological Map at a scale of 1:10,000, the best class was assigned to bedrock substrates, whereas the worst class was assigned to substrates consisting of Quaternary deposits. "Other" or undefined (N.A.) values were classified in an intermediate position in order to balance the uncertainty related to missing information.

Fig. 3. Map of the territory of the Autonomous Province of Trento showing the distinction between Quaternary deposits and outcropping or sub-outcropping bedrock.

Finally, the classification of structures with respect to the instability index aims to reflect those works located in catchments with a high propensity for the occurrence of debris flows. The instability index (an example is shown in Fig. 4) is an areal index defined as the intersection between debris-flow initiation points and active shallow landslides (Provincial Landslide Inventory) within a given catchment. The values of the instability index were subdivided into three classes using the *natural breaks* classification method.

Fig. 4. Instability index map (Cismon torrent catchment).

2.3 Development of a synthetic index

Based on the principles of ease of application and low subjectivity, and following several tests of potential indicators, the chosen approach was a summation of the scores assigned to the six factors described in the previous sections. Since it was necessary to discriminate the relative weight of each factor in determining the condition of potential fragility of a structure, a weighting of the scores was applied, in order to highlight the full range of situations within the study area.

Following various tests, the residual hazard index for each individual transverse protection structure was defined as the weighted sum of the class values of the selected factors:

$$\text{Index} = (\text{Fatt1} * \text{P1}) + (\text{Fatt2} * \text{P2}) + (\text{Fatt3} * \text{P3}) + (\text{Fatt4} * \text{P4}) + (\text{Fatt5} * \text{P5}) + (\text{Fatt6} * \text{P6}).$$

where:

- Factor 1 → year of construction of the structure;
- Factor 2 → height of the structure;
- Factor 3 → construction material of the structure;
- Factor 4 → landslide hazard at the structure site;
- Factor 5 → substrate at the structure site;
- Factor 6 → instability index;

and **P** represents the weighting factor used to balance the contribution of each factor within the equation for the calculation of the final index.

The index value was assigned to each individual structure contained in the provincial database through a calculation performed on the attribute table previously constructed in ArcGIS, using the *Field Calculator* tool. Again using ArcGIS, a classification of the resulting index values was performed in order to easily identify those structures that exhibit conditions of higher fragility.

The choice of calculating the index as a weighted sum of factors derives from the fact that this calculation is straightforward and easily verifiable, and that the attribution of a weight to each factor allows the sensitivity of the index to the various possible combinations to be adjusted in a relatively simple manner. Tests showed that not all factors have the same influence and that their appropriate weighting can result in a better correspondence with the potential fragility condition of the structures.

2.4 Definition of monitoring priority levels

Once the value of the synthetic index has been determined for each structure, it is of interest to classify the entire torrent control system to which the structures belong. While the identification of potentially fragile individual structures is important for guiding monitoring activities and possible interventions, the recognition of critical conditions at the scale of entire torrent control systems is also relevant from a management perspective. It should be emphasized that these two spatial scales should not be regarded as alternatives, but rather as complementary, and that the results obtained from the application of the indices must be interpreted in light of the knowledge and experience of the personnel responsible for catchment management.

The final step of the methodology therefore required the definition of a level of fragility (and, prospectively, monitoring priority) for torrent control systems. This requires the aggregation of the index values of individual structures to the scale of the entire system in which they are located (the *forest-hydraulic system*, as defined by the Autonomous Province of Trento). Using ArcGIS, a *spatial join* operation was carried out, which assigns to a single polygon (representing a torrent control system) the index values of all individual structures contained within it. The resulting value was calculated as the median of all selected values.

Analogously to what was done for the classification of the index, monitoring priority levels were also subdivided into three classes, in order to facilitate the identification of torrent control systems that contain a high number of structures in conditions of potential fragility.

3. Results

3.1 Definition of the index and classification

The evaluation of the factors used for the determination of the index resulted in the definition, for each factor, of three quality classes associated with three different scores. These scores were then used to compute the index for each individual structure in the database.

The weighted-sum index is defined as:

$$\text{Indice_Sum_P} = (v_Fatt1*1) + (v_Fatt2*0.66) + (v_Fatt3*0.33) + (v_Fatt4*1) + (v_Fatt5*0.66) + (v_Fatt6*0.33)$$

where

v_Fatt1,v_Fatt2,v_Fatt3,... indicate the value of each individual factor defined for each structure.

The index was calculated for 16,096 structures contained in the dataset (referable to torrent control works) and shows a minimum value of 3.9 and a maximum value of 11.2 (Tab. 3).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the index values for the analysed dataset

No.	16096
Mean	7.2
Std. Dev.	1.2
Max	11.2
Min	3.9
Median	7.3

As in previous steps, the index value was assigned to each individual structure in the provincial database through a calculation performed on the attribute table using the *Field Calculator* tool in ArcGIS. A classification of the resulting index values was then carried out in ArcGIS in order to easily identify those structures that are in more critical conditions.

The structure database counts 16,096 structures and for each a fragility index was calculated. The maximum, minimum and mean values of the index are as follows: max=11.2, min=3.9, mean=7.2.

Based on these values, the index was classified according to three fragility classes (Fig. 5 and 6): low = 3.9-6.4; medium = 6.4-8.8; high = 8.8-11.2. The evaluation led to identification of 2,631 structures with high fragility.

Fig. 5. Classification of check dams into three classes (equal interval criterion) based on the values of the fragility index.

Fig. 6. Fragility index of check dams over the entire territory of the Autonomous Province of Trento.

Several torrent control systems were analysed in order to evaluate the correspondence between the index values and the actual condition of the structures, as assessed through field observations or, as in the case of the Rotiano stream, on the basis of the occurrence of events that caused check-dam failures. Figure 7 shows the classification of structures for the Rotiano stream—primary focus of the present project—in the situation preceding the debris flow of 29 October 2018, and for the Antermont stream (Fassa Valley),

where a series of check dams representative of recurrent construction typologies and construction periods within the provincial territory is present.

As expected, numerous check dams along the Rotiano stream, including all those located in the upper part of the catchment—whose failure subsequently triggered the collapse of downstream structures—were classified within the highest fragility class. In the case of the Antermont stream, most structures fall within the intermediate class. Field observations conducted in this catchment appear to be in good agreement with the results of the indicator: the structures do not exhibit evident damage (Fig. 8), perform their function correctly, and are not currently threatened by landslides. However, the relative age of the structures and the possibility of intense sediment-transport events (most likely debris floods, but with the potential for debris flows in the case of paroxysmal phenomena) could prove critical for these structures.

Fig. 7. Results of the application of the structure fragility index to the Rotiano and Antermont catchments.

Fig. 8. Stone masonry check dam on the Antermont stream.

3.2 Definition of monitoring priority levels

The assessment of monitoring priority was carried out on 805 polygons representing the total number of forest-hydraulic systems defined for the Autonomous Province of Trento, encompassing all 16,096 analysed structures. The classification of priority level gave rise to three attention classes based on the median score calculated for each torrent control system: low class = 3.9-6.1; medium class = 6.1-8.2; high class = 8.2-10.3 (Fig. 9). The evaluation allowed identification of 134 torrent control systems for which the proposed indicator suggests high priority for monitoring structure state (Tab. 4).

Fig. 9. Classification of torrent control systems into three classes (equal interval criterion) based on fragility index values.

Tab. 4. Classification of torrent control systems based on structure fragility index

Tot (n.)	805
High (n.)	134
Moderate (n.)	442
Low (n.)	229

As an example, Figure 10 shows the classification of the torrent control systems of the Rotiano stream and the Antermont stream, which fall respectively into the highest and intermediate fragility classes (and thus monitoring and intervention priority).

Fig. 10. Generalisation of fragility levels to the entire torrent control systems of the Rotiano and Antermont streams.

The monitoring of torrent control works and systems presenting critical conditions may involve a series of complementary activities, including—though not limited to—the following:

- field observations of the condition of the structures;
- retrieval of original design documents, where available;
- collection of all available information on construction works (site setup and activity periods, construction techniques);
- reconstruction of the chronology of floods and debris flows that affected the catchment;

- detailed investigations of landslides and sediment sources within the catchment (complementing provincial-scale information).

Field observations may be conducted at different levels of detail. The simplest level consists of visual inspection of the condition of the structures, integrated with photographic documentation. More detailed investigations—required for “key” structures or in the presence of elements indicating potential critical conditions—may involve analyses of material conditions and other aspects related to the structural configuration of the works.

Field observations are also essential to assess the correspondence between the results of the proposed fragility indicator and actual field conditions. In this context, field surveys may also support refinements of the index itself.

During the project, targeted field surveys were conducted to assess the condition of check dams in the catchments of the Rio Secco di Besenello and the Rio Merdar. The Rio Secco is a left-bank tributary of the Adige River; its catchment, located within the municipality of Besenello, drains an area of 6.77 km². The Rio Merdar originates at the head of the Val di Susà in the municipality of Pergine Valsugana and flows into Lake Caldonazzo; its catchment drains an area of 3.56 km².

The selection of these two catchments was based on the prior knowledge of presumed critical conditions by the staff of the Servizio Bacini montani. It was possible to observe that the structures presenting the most significant structural problems—highlighted by blue ellipses in Figures 11 and 12—are correctly identified among those with the highest fragility according to the values of the synthetic index described above.

In the case of the Rio Secco, particular attention is required for the two upstream check dams, constructed at the toe of a large landslide affecting the right valley slope (Fig. 11). In the Rio Merdar catchment, several check dams in the middle–upper reach of the torrent show structural damage caused by the thrust exerted by landslide-affected slopes (Figs. 12 and 14).

Fig. 11. Fragility index values of structures and landslide hazard in the Rio Secco catchment.

Fig. 12. Fragility index values of structures and landslide hazard in the Rio Merdar catchment.

Fig. 13. Damaged stone masonry check dam in the Rio Secco catchment.

Fig. 14. Concrete check dam on the Rio Merdar: the wing wall is detached from the main body of the structure due to the thrust of the landslide-affected slope.

The retrieval of original design documents and the collection of information on construction practices may be difficult, particularly for older structures, but—where feasible—it can help identify potential weaknesses that are not clearly evident from visual inspection alone. In particular, the analysis of design documents can verify whether existing structures comply with current safety standards.

The final two aspects mentioned above—event chronology and sediment sources—are both directly or indirectly related to sediment dynamics within the catchment. While the relationship between intense torrential activity and the functionality and preservation of torrent control works may appear straightforward, it is important to acknowledge the complexity of interactions between these factors. For example, a catchment characterised by infrequent paroxysmal torrential events may convey a misleading sense of safety. If check dams were constructed following an extreme event, they may never have been subjected to forcing conditions of comparable severity.

Referring again to the case of the Rotiano stream, it is worth noting that despite the relatively low frequency of debris flows and the presence of an array of concrete check dams, the perception of persistent hazard conditions had not diminished. This led to the construction of new deposition areas that partially attenuated the effects of the extreme debris flow of 29 October 2018.

Beyond focusing on structures and systems presenting critical conditions, monitoring activities should also consider cases of particularly successful torrent control interventions. This refers to structures and systems that have performed—and continue to perform—the functions for which they were designed and constructed, and that have withstood severe hydro-meteorological and sediment-transport stresses. Attention to successful cases serves a dual purpose: first, they can provide examples to emulate—subject to necessary updates reflecting technological advances—and second, they are essential for communicating the importance and effectiveness of mountain torrent control works.

Among the many cases of good performance in response to high-intensity torrential events, Figures 15 and 16 present two examples related to deposition areas equipped with filtering check dams.

Fig. 15. Removal of deposits from the debris flow of 14 August 2010 from the deposition basin of the Rio Val del Lago.

Fig. 16. Torrential deposits—partly attributable to a debris flow and partly to a debris flood—mobilised by the event of 5 August 2022 and retained by a filtering check dam on the Rio Udai.

4. Notes on mitigation strategies

Among the measures aimed at mitigating the effects of the failure of torrent control works, the first and most obvious is the maintenance of check dams and the repair of damaged structures. However, such interventions may be difficult to implement due to accessibility constraints and, above all, due to the challenges of ensuring modern safety standards during worksite activities. In this respect, the previously mentioned Rio Secco di Besenello (Figs. 11 and 13) represents an emblematic case, given the difficulties in accessing the upstream check dams located in a channel reach affected by active landslides and rockfall hazard.

Where it is not feasible to maintain all the check dams of a torrent control system, it is appropriate to identify and consolidate one or more **key structures** capable of performing their function even when the contribution of other check dams to channel stabilization and/or sediment retention is lost. An example of this type of intervention—outside the Trentino territory—is the consolidation of a check dam on the Moscardo stream near the confluence with a right-bank tributary (Rio Lares), together with the redesign of the terminal reach of that tributary. Figure 17 shows a check dam that was severely undercut and whose right wing wall was disarticulated due to the thrust of a deep-seated, slow-moving landslide affecting the

right slope (Marcato et al., 2012). The same landslide had damaged the control works along the terminal reach of the Rio Lares, which consisted of a channel with a corrugated metal bed supported by concrete sills and banks (Fig. 18a). A new massive reinforced-concrete check dam was constructed downstream of the previous one (Fig. 19), and the terminal reach of the Rio Lares was reconfigured with a series of timber sills (Fig. 18b), whose flexibility has so far allowed them to accommodate landslide movement without damage. These interventions date back to the second half of the 1990s and have since successfully withstood debris flows of significant—though not extreme—severity.

Fig. 17. Moscardo stream (Carnic Alps): check dam at the confluence with the Rio Lares.

Fig. 18. Torrent control works on the terminal reach of the Rio Lares before and after rehabilitation.

Fig. 19. New check dam on the Moscardo stream at the confluence with the Rio Lares.

The selection of key structures to be preserved and consolidated requires a thorough catchment-scale analysis, to be conducted through field observations and the examination of geological and geomorphological conditions. It may also benefit from numerical modelling approaches that allow the evaluation of scenarios involving the abandonment of torrent control systems and/or the removal (or conservation) of individual check dams (e.g. Mertin, 2018; Ramirez et al., 2022). These modelling approaches appear worthy of further development to enable their application across different morphological settings and various types of flow processes (debris flows, debris floods, and water floods).

A further mitigation option—one that interferes only marginally with existing works and does not affect those located in the upper reaches of the torrent—is the construction of modern torrent control structures downstream of systems exhibiting potential critical conditions. For these new structures, it is essential to identify sites located upstream of exposed infrastructures while simultaneously controlling a significant portion of the catchment that includes the main sediment sources capable of feeding debris flows and sediment-laden floods, including debris floods. Such new works may consist of deposition basins equipped with filtering check dams. The experience of the Rotiano stream demonstrates that these structures are effective in retaining material, including sediment released by the potential failure of upstream check dams, thereby moderately attenuating event severity downstream. The same case, however, also highlights that in the event of a debris flow accompanied by the cascading collapse of multiple check dams, these new deposition basins may not be sufficient to prevent downstream damage.

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